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3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable is the main outcome of Tasks 3.1 (Review of 'risk aversion', 'risk cooperation' and 'risk normalization' concepts according to the climate change adaptation literature) and 3.2 (Identify which driving-factors characterize 'risk management' and how to be integrated as part of a 'risk aversion' module for behavior modelling). It will describe how the 'risk aversion' module previously developed in the MODFABE project has been characterized and updated with new insights from a literature review process. According to the project specific objectives (SO), this deliverable aims to standardize 'risk aversion' concept from social data and identify main drivers and standards for their inclusion in behaviour modelling (SO2), while accomplish with risk management patterns in a pre-tested Agent-Based Model (ABM) (SO3).

The target audience is both external (public) and internal (BECLICK team). Its results will be used to reinforce Task 2.6 (Characterize farmers' and irrigation districts' profiles and check the 'neighboring effect') and the related Task 3.3 (Check 'risk normalization' patterns from WP2 results), and Task 4.1 (Validate the 'risk aversion' module).

The BECLICK project gives continuity to the methods and results obtained in the MODFABE project (H2020-MSCA-IF-2018, GA 832464) to reinforce risk management on climate change by delving into farmers' and irrigation districts' adaptive capacity, considering heuristics and social-learning as inputs for behavior modelling regarding climate change awareness, impacts, and adaptation measures and barriers. BECLICK includes different case studies, delving into the analysis of the Italian case study (Lake Como) to then potentially replicate the approach to case studies from Europe (Spain), the United States (California), Africa (Mozambique) and Asia (Vietnam). Case studies are connected to two international projects in which the IP together with the team members are involved: GONEXUS (www.gonexus.eu) and SOSWATER (www.sos-water.eu). This deliverable runs in parallel to similar research conducted in both projects to update risk preferences and risk normalization patterns.

4 INTRODUCTION

Risk preference is an essential element of agricultural decision-making, reflecting a fundamental aspect of human personality. To model agricultural decision-making realistically, it is essential to capture the intricate complexity of individual behaviour and interactions within farming communities. Agent-based models (ABMs) have emerged as a valuable and widely used tool for this purpose. They provide an effective framework to simulate the dynamics of decision-making among farmers, allowing for a fine representation of the factors influencing choices in the agricultural sector.

During the MODFABE project, we identified some vague definitions –most of them from a qualitative perspective– able to define the complexity of risk aversion applied to climate change adaptation research. In this context, BECLICK seeks to advance in risk aversion analysis that allow a most robust knowledge on how to integrate risk assessment into behavior modelling on climate change awareness, perception, and adaptive capacity at the local scale. A mutual language across disciplines (e.g., geography, agronomy, water management, engineering, etc.) will be reinforced by combining learnings, limitations, and gaps from the MODFABE project and new insights from the most recent literature, which will be tracked explicitly through the prism of different risk aversion profiles to be performed through the risk aversion model developed in the ABNexus model.

The document is structured as follows: After the Introduction, Section 2 provides the results of the literature review process focused on 1) how risk aversion is conceptualized and defined from different perspectives, 2) which are the main data sources used to characterize the concept –considering both qualitative and quantitative approaches–, 3) what drivers explain the application of the concept and contributes to their formulation, and 4) some examples of its application in similar contexts for replicability. Section 3 presents the ABNexus as the framework in which the risk aversion module was developed and need to be reinforced through the results of the previous section. This piece includes 1) a framework overview (including main remarks on model execution and decision process), 2) the description of the risk aversion module and the risk aversion criteria, and 3) predefined risk aversion profiles. Section 4 closes the report with key points and final remarks.

5 LITERATURE REVIEW ON RISK AVERSION

This section explores the concept of risk aversion in recent scientific literature. It examines how risk aversion has been characterized and the implications it has for farming activities, with a focus on agent-based modeling. The section highlights key studies that have used agent-based modeling to investigate the complex relationship between risk aversion and farming practices.

5.1 The concept

Risk preference plays a fundamental role in shaping decision-making within the agricultural sector, a concept extensively explored in the scientific literature (e.g., Nie et al., 2021). It is ingrained as a fundamental personality characteristic in humans, embodying both objective and subjective dimensions (Nie et al., 2021). The objective facet, often easier and more straightforward to estimate, offers insights into quantifiable elements that influence decision-making in farming contexts. In contrast, the subjective component delves into farmers' emotions, perceptions, experiences, and expectations related to specific agricultural activities. This subjective lens provides a direct assessment of self-perception, connected to personal experiences and self-evaluations of efficacy and personality (e.g., Taberna et al., 2023)

Risk preference proves to be a decisive factor in determining reactions to natural hazards in agriculture, (e.g., Cassar et al., 2017). The scientific community, recognizing the multifaceted nature of risk preferences, employs a range of methodologies for investigation. Econometrics and surveys are extensively utilized (e.g., Oyinbo et al., 2019), with various techniques developed for empirical testing. Other examples include lottery choice task decisions, self-assessment questions, willingness to pay assessments, and hypothetical gambles (e.g., Sanapati, 2020). These approaches collectively contribute to a better understanding of the ways in which risk preferences shape decision-making in agriculture and farm management.

Integrating risk preferences into the modeling of agricultural decision-making requires an approach that can capture the complexity of individual behaviors and interactions within farming communities. Agent-based models (ABMs) have established as a valuable and popular tool for this purpose, providing a powerful framework to explore interactions among farmers and their environment (e.g., Huber et al., 2018; Sun et al., 2016). In ABMs, each farmer is modelled as an autonomous agent with a set of personal characteristics, including risk preferences, accurately capturing the diversity and heterogeneity in decision-making processes (Sun et al., 2016). ABMs are especially useful in simulating land-use changes, employing a process-based 'bottom-up' approach that captures emergent phenomena such as changes in farm activities and ecosystem service provision. The strength of this modeling approach lies in its potential capability to incorporate cognitive, emotional, personal, and social factors that underlie human behavior, necessary for capturing the full complexity of farmers' decision-making (e.g., Brown et al., 2020; Dessart et al., 2019).

Furthermore, ABMs facilitate the exploration of feedback loops between human decisions and environmental systems, enabling the investigation of emergent patterns in time and space resulting from interactions at lower organizational levels (e.g., Bonabeau, 2002). This explicit representation of individual-level dynamics is crucial for comprehending the consequences of decision-making. While the simplicity of decision-making rules specified at the individual level can lead to emergent system dynamics, it is important to acknowledge the limitations imposed by incomplete knowledge and data availability (e.g., Sun et al., 2016). Complex ABMs necessitate a significant amount of empirical data for a detailed representation (e.g., Balbi et al., 2013), to capture the heterogeneity of entities and the intricacies of their mutual interactions (e.g., Manson et al. 2012).

Within the broader realm of climate-change risk assessments and adaptation strategies for farming activities, accurately comprehending, and modeling human behavior poses a significant challenge, particularly within coupled human-natural systems (Huber et al., 2022). Among the complex interplay of socio-economic priorities and environmental interactions, the modeling of risk aversion is a critical aspect as it significantly influences a farmer's decision-making process (Huber et al., 2022). Shaping the foundational assumptions of underlying behavioral models becomes imperative. In fact, farmers may deviate from purely income-maximizing strategies for diverse reasons. First, they might adhere to certain established practices despite available information or policy changes (e.g., Möhring et al., 2020; Giannoccaro & Berbel, 2013). Second, decisions may be guided by hidden risk behavior (e.g., Böcker et al. 2020, Möhring et al., 2020). Third, social networks can exert a significant influence on decision-making processes, further complicating the dynamics of risk aversion in agricultural choices (e.g., Huber et al., 2022).

These deviations from purely rational, income-maximizing strategies highlight the intricate and context-specific nature of risk aversion in farmers' decision-making processes. Therefore, accurately incorporating risk aversion into agent-based models (ABMs) is crucial for generating realistic insights into future projections of adaptation and response to climate change.

5.2 Main data sources

Agent-based modelling (ABM) in farm decision-making has garnered numerous contributions. Traditionally, models assumed farmers pursued maximum profit, with foundational works by Balmann (1997) and Berger (2001) serving as pillars. Several contributions have then expanded on this foundation and contributed to the evolution of more contemporary and modular modelling approaches. Models have explored various aspects of farm decision-making, including:

Crop selection: Berger & Troost (2014) developed an ABM to simulate crop choice in an agricultural system, incorporating factors such as farmer preferences, soil characteristics, and market prices.

Irrigation systems: Holtz & Nebel (2014) and van Duinen et al. (2016) included the transition from rainfed to irrigated agriculture and the process of investment and adoption of new technologies.

These early ABMs have laid a strong foundation for more advanced models that capture the multifaceted nature of farm decision-making. Recent efforts have moved beyond the simplistic profit-maximizing paradigm, incorporating concepts such as bounded rationality, risk aversion, and social interactions.

However, recent efforts aim for greater realism by moving beyond the simplistic profit-maximizing paradigm. Notably, there's a shift towards acknowledging bounded rationality, where farmers operate within cognitive limitations or resource constraints. They may not have perfect information about their environment or the consequences of their actions. They may also have limited time and resources to make decisions. As a result, farmers may often make decisions that are sub-optimal in terms of profit maximization.

The incorporation of bounded rationality has also led to the development of more context-specific ABMs. For example, Groeneveld et al. (2017) developed an ABM that models how farmers make decisions about crop choice, considering factors such as their risk preferences and their limited knowledge of soil conditions. They used a utility function to represent the value that farmers place on different crop yields. Schlüter et al. (2017) developed an ABM that models how farmers make decisions about investment in agricultural machinery, considering their risk preferences and their limited access to credit. The authors used a heuristic called loss aversion to represent the tendency of farmers to be more sensitive to losses than to gains.

Other models provided a paradigm shift by exploring the factors influencing decision-making, including risk aversion and preferences. Magliocca et al. (2015) focus on land-use decisions in coupled human-natural systems. Their model considers the interactions between farmers' decisions and the surrounding environment. They used a utility function to represent the value that farmers place on different land-use options. They also used a heuristic

called the "sunk cost fallacy" to represent the tendency of farmers to stick with decisions that they have already made, even if they are not the best long-term options. Murray-Rust et al. (2014), on the other hand, present a generic and modular approach to understanding land-use decisions and policy impacts. They used a Bayesian network to model the decision-making process of farmers. A Bayesian network is a type of probabilistic graphical model that can represent the relationships between different variables, capturing the complex interactions between farmers' preferences, the environment, and policy interventions. Their model can be used to study a variety of land-use decisions, in different contexts, and with different policy interventions. Holtz & Nebel (2014) and Troost et al. (2015) include risk minimization besides profit maximization and introduced penalties for more risky crops. Van Duinen et al. (2016) define the uncertainty level as the ratio between farmers' current income and predicted one (based on past experience). Schultze et al. (2016) adopt heterogeneous discount rates to reflect personal risk aversion of the agents. However, risk aversion and decision-making uncertainty is still limited (Huber et al., 2018).

5.3 Drivers

By acknowledging that farmers are not always rational actors, these models can better capture the diversity of decision-making processes that occur on farms. Several contributions have highlighted the most significant non-economic driver that must be taken into account. As notable examples, Taberna et al. (2018) investigated the role of social norms in shaping farmer behaviour, finding that farmers are more likely to adopt certain practices if they are perceived as being socially acceptable within their communities. Heerink et al. (2014) studied the adoption of precision agriculture technologies by farmers in the Netherlands. They found that farmers who were more connected to other farmers who were using these technologies were also more likely to adopt them themselves. Filatova et al. (2015) explored the influence of information availability on farmer decision-making, demonstrating that farmers are more likely to adopt sustainable practices when they have access to reliable information about the benefits and risks involved. Jager and Janssen (2015) examined the impact of environmental feedback on farmer behaviour, finding that farmers are more responsive to environmental changes when they have direct experience with the consequences of their actions.

By considering the specific characteristics of different agricultural systems, models can provide more accurate predictions of how farmers will respond to changes in their environment and policies. However, despite the advancements, Huber et al. (2018) provide a compelling critique of current ABMs, highlighting their persistent emphasis on income maximization and the use of expected utility theory. They argue that these simplifications fail to capture the complexity of human decision-making, where factors like risk aversion play a pivotal role. To address these limitations, Huber et al. (2018, 2020, 2022) developed the FARMIND framework, a novel approach to modelling farm decision-making that incorporates the following principles:

Agent Heterogeneity: FARMIND allows for the representation of a diverse range of farmers, each with its unique characteristics, preferences, and decision-making processes. This reflects the reality of farms, where farmers vary in their experiences, knowledge, and risk tolerance. Moreover, FARMIND goes beyond mere representation and incorporates a mechanism for simulating the evolution of these characteristics over time (Huber et al., 2022), capturing how farmers learn, adapt, and adjust as they acquire new knowledge and experience.

Adaptive Learning: FARMIND incorporates the ability of farmers to learn from their experiences and adapt their decision-making accordingly. This is crucial for capturing the dynamic nature of agricultural systems, where farmers continuously refine their practices based on new information and feedback.

Network Interactions: FARMIND explicitly represents the social networks in which farmers are embedded and how these networks influence their behaviour. This recognizes the importance of social interactions in shaping farmer decision-making, as farmers often seek information, advice, and support from their peers and communities, and that these interactions can influence their adoption of new practices or technologies. FARMIND further incorporates a mechanism for simulating the emergence of social norms and conventions within these networks (Huber et al., 2022), demonstrating how social interactions can collectively influence farm decision-making and ultimately shape the trajectory of agricultural practices.

Huber et al. (2022) applied the FARMIND framework to simulate the adoption of various weed control strategies in a Swiss alpine region, demonstrating the model's ability to capture the complex interplay between farmer behaviour, social interactions, and environmental factors in shaping weed management practices.

6 THE ABNEXUS

This section introduces the agent-based model developed for the GONEXUS and BECLICK projects. We provide an extensive description of the behavioural modules and risk aversion assessment framework employed, providing a concise overview of its capacity to simulate diverse decision-making styles of farmers under varying levels of information access and risk tolerance. The section begins with a general overview of the main components of the model. Then show the three distinct behavioural modules – perfect foresight, blind, and FARMIND – and their unique approaches to dealing with uncertainty and decision-making under incomplete information. It then delves into the risk aversion assessment framework, explaining how we tailor risk aversion criteria to each module's decision-making process. Finally, it unveils how we incorporate real-world risk attitudes into the model by extracting risk aversion profiles from survey data, enhancing its ability to simulate irrigation decisions with greater accuracy.

6.1 Framework

The purpose of the model is to simulate agricultural production decisions, reflecting the heterogeneity in farmers' decision-making processes under climate change conditions. The model is based both on standard economic concepts of profit maximization, and advanced behavioural concepts such as risk preferences and social influence within the decisional process.

Figure 1: ABNexus framework

The model integrates information from the soil-moisture balance crop optimal-growth model that simulates the physical layer with farmer agents that react by taking decisions to maximize their expected utility. It is intended to evaluate the impacts of local decisions on crop production and water efficiency at the system level for large CHNSs under climate or policy changes.

Figure 2 shows the main components of the agent-based model and how they interact with each other and the surrounding framework. Here follows a short description for each component.

Central Module [M]: module in charge of coordinating the overall execution. It synchronizes the different components through annual time steps and different decisional phases.

IdrAgra Wrapper [IdW]: wrapper unit that interacts with the IdrAgra model. It abstracts the soft-link by managing the setup of simulation settings, creating the appropriate execution sandbox, launching simulations, dealing with parallelization, and retrieving output data back to agents.

Domain grid [D]: internal representation for the spatial domain. Comprises thousands of Field-Cell units [C], representing a 250 square-meter field each.

Farmer Agent [FA]: main decisional entity representing a specific farm of the domain. It owns and, therefore, has exclusive decisional power on a sequence of Field-Cells. Its decisions address crop type and irrigation technology adopted. Farmer may be characterized by an internal forage demand (due to livestock activity) which has influential power on their decision. Each farmer agent may be initialized with a different behavioral attitude, providing a significant decisional heterogeneity at system level. Farmer agents have awareness of their spatial placement and may influence or be influenced by their neighbors.

Irrigation unit [CZ] (comizio): hierarchical unit which represents association with influential power on belonging farm agents.

Market [Mk]: module represents exogenous market dynamics for crop prices, which are the primary income source for Farms.

Governor [Gv]: module gives logical representation to national or regional public administration, which has influential power on agents through specific policies like subsidies to give incentive to the transition towards water-efficient technologies.

Figure 2: main components of the agent-based model and basic interactions schema

6.2 Behavioral modules

Here we delineate the implementation of behaviour and risk aversion heterogeneity, with Farmers who may exhibit a wide range of decision-making styles, from those who prioritize profit maximization to those who are more risk-averse or who place greater weight on social norms or environmental considerations. Recognizing the multifaceted nature of risk aversion, we explore three distinct implementations that offer insights into various aspects of farmers' behaviour. The first approach aligns with the concept of perfect rationality, modelling farmers as profit maximizers making decisions based on fully rational economic principles. The second approach incorporates past performance feedback into farmers' decision-making process, reflecting the influence of experience on their risk assessment. Finally, our third implementation draws inspiration from the FARMIND (Huber, 2022) and CONSUMAT (Jager & Janssen, 2012) behavioural models. By incorporating psychological factors such as risk perception and behavioural biases, as well as social influences from their peers and communities, this approach captures the complex interplay between individual characteristics and social norms that influence farmers' risk aversion.

6.2.1 Perfect Rational (Profit Maximizer)

The first implementation, aligned with the perfect rationality paradigm, assumes farmers act as profit maximizers. In this behavioural module, decision-making is driven solely by economic considerations, with farmers aiming to maximize their expected financial returns. This approach is grounded in classical economic theory, assuming that farmers possess complete information, make optimal choices based on utility maximization, and exhibit consistent risk attitudes. Within this behavioural module, the model systematically tests all potential solutions, selecting the one that maximizes the expected outcome expressed in monetary terms (inflows/outflows).

Agents within this module possess complete knowledge of past and future meteorological conditions, allowing them to perfectly optimize their decisions over time. This module serves as a base benchmark, to be compared with both historical patterns and future projections.

6.2.2 Memory-based performances

The second module introduces a memory-based approach, where farmers' decisions are influenced by past performances and general confrontation. This model recognizes the influence of experience on decision-making, acknowledging that farmers may draw upon their historical successes and failures when faced with similar situations. By incorporating memory into the decision process, we aim to capture the adaptive nature of farmers, who may adjust their risk attitudes based on previous outcomes. This approach provides a more dynamic and experiential dimension to the model, allowing for the evolution of risk aversion over time. Agents in this module retain perfect memory of past meteorological conditions but lack any forecasting capability, effectively operating under complete uncertainty. This module reflects the situation where farmers rely solely on past experience to guide their irrigation decisions.

6.2.3 FARMIND-inspired behavior

Incorporating a FARMIND-inspired behavioural module, inspired by Huber et al. (2022), aims to bring real-world and diverse decision-making into play. Going beyond the idea of perfect rationality, the FARMIND model offers a detailed perspective to grasp how psychological, social, and individual factors intricately influence farmers' choices in agriculture.

The FARMIND model, in its way of accounting for heterogeneous decision-making processes, focuses on following key aspects.

Handling Uncertainty: FARMIND embraces the uncertainty inherent in agriculture, providing a more realistic view of how farmers make decisions in the face of potential risks and rewards, moving away from deterministic approaches.

Socially-Influenced Behaviour: The model captures the impact of social networks and peer interactions on farming choices, recognizing the influence of human decision-making. It acknowledges the role of social cues and learning in individual decisions within agriculture.

Dynamics of Farming Preferences: FARMIND goes beyond the traditional profit-maximization assumption by explicitly representing farmers' individual goals, personal values, and preferences for specific activities. This inclusion leads to a more thorough understanding of the diverse factors influencing farming behaviour.

This is achieved by integrating key elements that move away from traditional ABMs based on perfect rationality:

Prospect Value: FARMIND introduces the concept of prospect value, in line with Cumulative Prospect Theory. This acknowledges psychological biases related to gains and losses, capturing the tendency to be more sensitive to losses than gains and to give more weight to small probabilities.

Social Network Dynamics: The model explicitly considers interactions in social networks, recognizing that farmers' decisions are shaped by the opinions and actions of their peers. This dynamic representation reflects the impact of social learning and information exchange on farming choices.

Individual Farming Preferences: FARMIND acknowledges that farmers' decisions are influenced by factors beyond profit maximization. This includes personal values, lifestyle preferences, and risk tolerance, offering a more detailed understanding of the diverse motivations guiding farming behaviour.

The FARMIND model adopts a structured three-step approach to delve into the farmers' decision-making:

1. **Heuristic Decision:** Farmers make heuristic decisions by selecting one of four strategies: Repetition (maintaining the status quo), Optimization (seeking the best choice based on available information), Imitation (following peer behaviour), or Inquiry (collecting and evaluating information from various sources).

2. **Fuzzy Preference Maps:** individual preferences for specific farming activities are considered by using fuzzy preference maps. This approach captures the relative importance of different practices and the potential resistance to change in established routines.

3. **Production Decision:** Farmers' production decisions are simulated through a bio-economic sub-model, integrating biophysical constraints and economic considerations. Constrained optimization ensures that production decisions align with overarching goals and preferences determined by the heuristic decision and fuzzy preference maps.

The integration of the FARMIND-inspired behavioural module marks a significant advancement in modelling the intricacies of farmers' decision-making within ABMs. This approach contributes to a more accurate understanding of the factors influencing agricultural behaviour and, consequently, the outcomes of agricultural systems in diverse and dynamic environments. By encompassing prospect theory, social network dynamics, and individual preferences, FARMIND offers a robust tool for comprehending how farmers navigate decisions amid uncertainty and social influences. This has profound implications for better simulating the impacts of agricultural policies, technologies, and market conditions, providing valuable insights into farmers' behaviour and the overall performance of agricultural systems.

6.3 Risk aversion criteria

Here, we explore the integration of Risk Aversion (RA) criteria into our model, aiming to examine and compare three distinct cases that capture various dimensions of farmers' behaviour. The first case involves a perfect maximizer without explicit consideration of risk aversion, aligning with a profit-maximizing approach grounded in economic rationality. The second case incorporates RA criteria based on past memory performances, acknowledging the influence of historical experiences on decision-making. The third case draws inspiration from the FARMIND model, introducing a comprehensive framework that integrates psychological and social factors into farmers' risk aversion profiles. The second and third cases are described in detail in the following subsections.

6.3.1 Memory-based RA criteria

This setup rearranges how farmers prefer options (based on calculated expected utility) at each decision point. The reshuffling is based on three different criteria, representing distinct levels of risk aversion. We considered three metrics for this: the Wald criterion, the Hurwicz criterion, and the Maximax criterion.

Wald's criterion (Wald, 1950), or Maximin criterion, suits a pessimistic decision maker, making it better for highly risk-averse individuals. People using this method go for the option that gives the maximum returns under the worst-case scenario. Underneath there is a cautious behavior and prepared for the least favorable situation:

$$a^* = \operatorname{argmax}_a (\min f(a, w))$$

The Maximax criterion, on the other hand, reflects an individual with a very optimistic outlook (making it more fitting for those comfortable with high risk). This criterion involves choosing the best option under the most favorable circumstances. It is formulated as:

$$a^* = \operatorname{argmax}_a (\max f(a, w))$$

Hurwicz's criterion (Hurwicz, 1951), also known as the optimism-pessimism rule, is a middle-of-the-way approach, that weighs the performances in both the most and least favorable circumstances. It is formulated as:

$$a^* = \operatorname{argmax}_a (\alpha \min f(a, w) + (1 - \alpha) \max f(a, w))$$

The parameter α allows weighting the two extreme scenarios, thus moving the scale of preference more towards a risk prone or risk averse behavior.

6.3.2 FARMIND-inspired criteria

Farmers as shown by Table 1 make heuristic decisions by selecting one of four strategies: Repetition, Optimization, Imitation, or Inquiry.

Table 1: Strategic decision and choice set.

		Satisfaction based on prospect value over experience	
		> 0: satisfied	< 0: dissatisfied
Information seeking behavior	< tolerance	Repetition: no changes from current behaviour	Optimization: search for expected utility maximizing action
	> tolerance	Imitation: free-ride on the cognitive effort.	Inquiry: ambition engage more in information processing for new activities.

Central to the strategic decision-making process, as in the FARMIND model, is the *satisfaction* dimension, that is the prospect value of farmer income. This dimension extends beyond immediate behavioral outcomes, by including future expectations amid uncertainty. In fact, farmers make decisions not solely based on current results but also by considering potential risks and rewards on the horizon.

$$V_i = \sum_{t=0}^{t_{mem}} v(x_t) \cdot \Phi(x_t)$$

The prospect value is calculated using agent specific value $v(x_t)$ and probability weighting functions $\Phi(x_t)$ for each income x_t over the memory length *mem*. If the sum of these incomes is positive, an agent is considered satisfied. Otherwise, it is unsatisfied.

Other pivotal factors influencing information-seeking behavior are the *dissimilarity index* of farming activities and the *similarity index* of economic performances. The linear combination of these two factors triggers two different behaviours on agent's information seeking.

Farmers, in fact, continuously assess the *dissimilarity* between their own farming practices and those of their peers in the social network:

$$d_i = \frac{1}{a} \sum_{j=1}^a \frac{\# \text{ peers performing } A_j}{n} \cdot (1 - P(A_j^i))$$

where *a* are all the activities performed, and $P(A_j^i)$ is agent's performance status for activity *j* (1 if performed, 0 otherwise).

When faced with high dissimilarity, farmers are prompted to question their approach and may react by seeking more information or adapting their strategies. The higher the value of d_i , the greater the similarity between an agent and their peers.

Likewise, another critical factor shaping information-seeking behaviour is the similarity index of economic performances. Farmers compare their income growth with that of their peers, and significant differences can

trigger reactions. This becomes particularly relevant in the face of shocks that may lead to diverse income outcomes within the farming community. The index is defined as:

$$g_i = G_{i,t} - \bar{G}_t$$

where:

$$G_{i,t} = \frac{x_{it} - \frac{\sum_{t-m}^{t-1} x_t}{m-1}}{\bar{x}_{i,m-1}}$$

is Agent i 's income growth for period t , and

$$\bar{G}_t = \frac{\bar{x}_{t-1} - \frac{\sum_{t-m}^{t-1} \bar{x}_j}{m-1}}{\bar{x}_{m-1}}$$

is the income growth of the entire population.

These indices provide a quantifiable means to capture the influence of social networks and peer interactions on farmers' decision-making processes. They reflect the dynamic nature of information-seeking behavior, acknowledging the impact of both farming activities and economic performances on individual choices.

To determine personal preferences, the FARMIND model employs fuzzy methods, allowing agents to assign values to each action. These values indicate the agent's preference or indifference between two compared actions. The non-dominance method is then employed to define a subset of preferable activities based on the agent's preferences. Fuzzy outranking methods, including non-domination scores, play a crucial role in ranking activities according to individual preferences. This process helps identify a subset of the best-preferred activities, offering insight into the nuanced and diverse personal preferences that shape farmers' decision-making.

When selecting a production strategy, the FARMIND model adheres to economic maximization principles. This involves optimizing production decisions based on economic considerations while considering overarching goals and preferences determined by the satisfaction and information-seeking dimensions.

In conclusion, the risk aversion criteria embedded in the FARMIND behavioral module provide a comprehensive and dynamic framework for understanding how farmers make strategic decisions. By integrating prospect value, dissimilarity and similarity indices, fuzzy methods, and economic maximization principles, the FARMIND model captures the heterogeneous nature of risk aversion in agricultural decision-making.

6.4 Risk aversion profiles

Risk aversion profiles have been estimated from survey data collected from farmers in the Lombardy region, developed as part of the MODFABE project (funded under the European Commission as part of the Excellence Science - Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions, H2020-MSCA-IF 2018, ID 832464, <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/832464>). The respondents were predominantly male (80%), and approximately 45% of them were aged over 55. The educational background varied widely, with 38% having completed tertiary education and 32% relying solely on vocational training. Most farmers had extensive experience in the sector, with 50% having worked for more than 30 years. A significant portion (69%) depended solely on income from farming, without engaging in other off-farm activities.

Labor dynamics varied, with 49% of farms relying only on family labor, while 40% also employed non-family labor. Traditional farming methods were prevalent, as 75% of farms utilized a conventional agricultural production system. Only a small percentage (11%) practiced organic/agroecological farming, and an even smaller portion (5%) were in the process of transitioning to it. Fertilizer usage was high (85%), with a majority (78%) employing mineral, compound, or organic fertilizers. Renewable Energy Sources (REs) were adopted by 37% of farms. The sizes of farms varied significantly, ranging from very small (2% less than 1 ha, 19% less than 5 ha) to very large (29% more than 50 ha). Most farms practiced irrigated agriculture (72%), with 17% relying on rainfed methods. Surface irrigation was the most common method (52%), followed by sprinkler and mixed systems (24%), and drip irrigation (7%). Canals were the primary water source (38%), followed by a mix of canals and wells (28%), and wells alone (12%). Non-conventional water sources, such as reclaimed water, were rarely used, implemented by only 3 of the 460 respondents.

Farmers demonstrated awareness of climate change issues and its impact on various sectors. There was a consensus on key contributing factors, including an increase in temperature and heat waves (88%), an increase in the frequency or intensity of drought events (88%), and an increased frequency or intensity of floods (76%). However, opinions diverged on the efficacy of human ingenuity in addressing climate change challenges, with 55% believing it to be insufficient. Additionally, 77% of the sample rejected the idea that agriculture could benefit from global climate changes.

To delineate distinct behavioral profiles among the surveyed farmers, we employed two complementary algorithms: Multiple Correspondence Analysis (MCA) and Hierarchical Clustering on Principal Components (HCPC). This approach, commonly utilized in analogous studies (Shukla et al., 2019; Montcho et al., 2022; Soltani and Mellah, 2022), proves effective in providing a comprehensive understanding of intricate and extensive datasets. Initially, MCA was applied to the dataset, involving the computation of new projected dimensions through a linear combination of selected active variables. This process enabled the representation of individuals in a newly derived multidimensional space, with each dimension explaining a distinct percentage of the initial dataset's variation, known as inertia. The resulting projected dimensions from MCA served as a foundational framework for subsequent analyses. Subsequently, the HCPC algorithm was implemented, orchestrating three integral steps: correlation analysis, hierarchical clustering, and k-means clustering. This amalgamation aimed to construct an optimized and robust partition of the initial dataset (Husson et al., 2010). The correlation analysis facilitated the exploration of relationships between variables, while hierarchical clustering organized individuals into groups based on similarities. Finally, k-means clustering further refined the partition, enhancing the precision of the identified clusters. Collectively, this dual algorithmic approach yielded two key outcomes. Firstly, it provided a condensed representation of the data, accentuating the most pertinent variables. Secondly, it facilitated the creation of clusters, grouping together individuals with similar characteristics. This methodology aligns with established practices in the literature and ensures a nuanced understanding of the diverse risk aversion profiles within the surveyed farming community.

The application of MCA and HCPC led to the identification of four distinct clusters, with the optimal number selected based on an optimization of the explained inertia. These clusters offer insights into the diverse risk aversion profiles prevalent among the surveyed farmers. Figure 2 visually represents the two most crucial dimensions emphasized by the analysis, namely irrigation type and farm size. Figure 3 provides a comprehensive depiction of the clusters mapped onto the same dimensions, offering a visual representation of the groupings. Cluster C2 emerges as the most discernible, comprising farmers exclusively engaged in rainfed agriculture. This clarity can be attributed to the prominent contribution of irrigation-related variables to the first dimension of the factor map. As shown in Figure 3, Cluster C2 is distinctly positioned in relation to the other clusters, reflecting the unique characteristics associated with rainfed agriculture. The remaining three clusters (C1, C3, C4) exhibit some overlap, as anticipated, given the less defining nature of other variables. Notably, farm size appears to play a partial role in explaining these clusters, with larger farms situated toward the bottom of the graph and smaller

ones positioned at the top. This observation aligns with expectations, as farm size often correlates with various farming practices and risk management strategies.

In summary, the clustering analysis provides valuable insights into the risk aversion profiles of Lombardy region farmers, emphasizing the role of irrigation type and farm size in shaping distinct clusters. Figures 2 and 3 visually enhance our understanding of these findings, illustrating the pivotal dimensions and the spatial arrangement of identified clusters.

Figure 3: Factor map representing the sample on the plane of the first two projected dimensions and highlighted based on their value in the two most relevant variables. On the left, the individuals are coloured based on their irrigation practice (irrigation, mixed practice, rainfed), on the right they are coloured based on the value of the farm size.

Figure 4: Result of the clustering algorithm. On the left, the individuals are mapped on the first two projected dimensions resulting from the MCA and coloured based on their assigned cluster. On the right, the distribution of individuals in the clusters is shown, highlighting the size difference in absolute numbers and percentages.

Here follows a detailed exploration of each identified cluster and its distinctive characteristics among Lombardy region farmers. To facilitate a comprehensive overview, Table 2 summarizes the most pivotal aspects associated with each cluster, providing a convenient reference point for key findings. Through this detailed analysis, we

unravel the nuanced risk aversion profiles that emerge from the clustering process, shedding light on factors such as irrigation practices, farm size, and other significant variables within each distinct cluster.

Cluster 1: This cluster is characterized by the highest average age, with 50% of its members surpassing 55 years. Notably, a substantial portion (33%) relies solely on vocational training, indicating a diverse educational background within the cluster. Despite being one of the older clusters, it boasts the highest level of experience in the farming sector, with 51% of individuals having dedicated more than 30 years to agriculture. Within Cluster 1, a significant majority of farms operate at the family level, with 64% relying exclusively on family labor. Furthermore, two-thirds of farmers in this cluster depend solely on income from farming, abstaining from any off-farm activities. A noteworthy aspect is that nearly half (49%) of these farmers express uncertainty regarding passing down their agricultural activities to the next generation, implying a potential lack of guaranteed generational continuity in farming. Examining the agricultural practices of Cluster 1, farmers predominantly own medium to large farms, with half of them exceeding 20 hectares in size. Despite being the largest cluster, their responses reflect some of the lowest average scores, with an overall average of 3.54 on a Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. This group's behavior closely aligns with the broader population, given its size. However, it stands out for having the highest proportion of unanswered or unknown responses (14%), suggesting a potential lack of interest, awareness, or knowledge, particularly in more technical aspects of the issues at hand.

Cluster 2: The individuals in this cluster are, on average, younger than those in Cluster 1, with 68% of them aged under 45. While still predominantly male, the proportion of women in this cluster exceeds the average at 36%. Moreover, Cluster 2 exhibits the second-highest education level, with 40% having completed tertiary education. This cluster is uniquely characterized by its exclusive engagement in rainfed agriculture, significantly influencing other farming characteristics. Farms within this cluster vary in size, predominantly falling within the medium to small range. A substantial portion (59%) adheres to conventional farming methods, although a noteworthy departure from the previous cluster is the increased adoption of organic methods (21%) and transitioning to organic practices (5%). In terms of awareness regarding climate change issues, this cluster demonstrates a relatively low score, like the previous group. However, it is noteworthy that more farmers in this cluster express skepticism about climate change being the most serious global problem (16% disagree with this, compared to the population average of 7%). The higher percentage of unanswered questions (18%, compared to the population average of 12%) could indicate a potential lack of awareness, interest, or knowledge within this group, contributing to their distinctive risk aversion profile.

Cluster 3: This cluster boasts the highest average age, with 51% of its members aged above 55 years. The education level within this cluster is relatively low, with 38% relying solely on vocational training. However, it stands out for having the highest level of experience in farming, with 63% of individuals dedicating more than 30 years to the sector. Farms associated with Cluster 3 tend to be significantly larger, with 86% having an area exceeding 50 hectares. Conventional agriculture is the predominant practice within this cluster, with 81% adhering to conventional methods. In terms of irrigation, surface irrigation is the preferred method for a majority (59%), while 27% employ a combination of surface irrigation and sprinkler systems. Canals (44%) and a mix of canals and wells (39%) serve as the primary water sources for these farms. An interesting aspect of this cluster is its stance on climate change, particularly in response to the statement in "Climate change is not a big issue because human ingenuity will enable us to adapt to changes". A notable 18% of farmers in this cluster agree to some extent, compared to the overall population average of 13%. Interestingly, Cluster 3 exhibits a much lower percentage of unanswered questions (7%) compared to the previous clusters, suggesting a higher level of engagement or awareness within this group.

Cluster 4: This cluster represents the youngest and most educated segment within the Lombardy farming community, offering a distinct risk aversion profile. A significant 72% of individuals in this cluster are below the age of 55, with 50% having attended tertiary education, showcasing the highest educational attainment among the clusters. Interestingly, despite being in a predominantly male-dominated sector, this cluster has a relatively

high female presence, reaching 38%. Furthermore, this group has the lowest average experience in farming, with only 18% having more than 30 years of experience. Farms associated with Cluster 4 tend to be smaller in size, with 69% covering less than 5 hectares. Organic agriculture is a prevalent practice within this cluster, with 41% of farmers engaging in it, or transitioning to it, while only one-third (31%) adhere strictly to traditional practices. Drip irrigation is the most common method employed by 72% of farmers, with wells serving as the primary water source for 44% of the farms. Remarkably, Cluster 4 exhibits the second-highest implementation of Renewable Energy Sources (RESs) at 47%, with solar energy being the most commonly adopted form (34%). Notably, every individual in this cluster agrees with the statement "Climate change is the single most serious problem facing the world." Moreover, they display the highest perception of climate change impacts, identifying an average of 10 out of the proposed 14 impacts. The most frequently selected impacts include increased frequency or intensity of droughts (97%), an increase in temperature and heat waves (94%), increased frequency or intensity of floods (88%), new or worsened pest infections (88%), and changes in vegetation species and biodiversity (88%). Cluster 4 stands out for having the lowest percentage of unanswered questions (4%), underscoring a high level of engagement and awareness within this group.

Table 2 Clusters and most relevant defining characteristics

Cluster	Name	Key Attitude	Notes
C1	Adapted through crop diversification	Most isolated	Lowest score in AD18 - cooperation with farming community (38%)
C2	Adapted through cooperation	Most insecure	Highest percentage of IDKs answers (18%)
C3	Adapted through insurance	Most confident	Highest percentage of farmers that agree with AW2 - human ingenuity as solution for climate change. (18%)
C4	Adapted through climate services	Most aware	Highest percentage of farmers that agree with AW1 - climate change as the most important current. problem (97%)

To further categorize these clusters, they were classified as either "Risk Taker," "Risk Averse," or "Risk Neutral" based on a comprehensive set of indicators. As highlighted in Table 3, Cluster 1 (C1) consistently exhibits risk-averse tendencies across all proposed indicators. In contrast, Cluster 4 (C4) emerges as a risk-taking group, demonstrating a proactive approach towards risk management. Cluster 3 (C3) presents a varied picture, showcasing different risk attitudes depending on the specific variables considered. Therefore, the attitudes assigned to the clusters were designated as "Risk Averse" for Cluster 1, "Partially Risk Averse" for Cluster 3, and "Risk Taker" for Cluster 4. Notably, the absence of Cluster 2 (C2) in this analysis stems from its dependence on rainfed irrigation, which is not applicable to the Adda river domain area upon which the model was based. Consequently, Cluster 2 was excluded from the risk categorization.

This comprehensive analysis sheds light on the diverse risk aversion profiles within the Lombardy farming community, providing a foundation for targeted interventions and policies that consider the unique characteristics and perspectives of each cluster.

Table 3: Comparison of risk aversion levels assignment, considering similar cases in the literature. Possible proxy variables are searched for in the literature, and a label is assigned to each cluster considering that variable. The overall label (used in the ABM implementation) is assigned considering the average behaviour of each cluster. The codes are RA for Risk Averse, RT for Risk Taker, RN for Risk Neutral

Variable	Avg	C1	C3	C4	Criterion	C1	C3	C4
Insurance Use	61%	58%	84%	41%	The higher insurance use, the higher the risk aversion.	RA	RA	RT
Age	53	54	54	57	The older, the higher the risk aversion.	RA	RA	RT
Fertilizers use	85%	90%	92%	72%	The higher fertilizers usage, the higher the risk aversion.	RA	RA	RT
Reduce fertilizers	70%	65%	81%	88%	The higher, the lower the risk aversion.	RA	RT	RT
Avg. number of new technologies (adaptation) implemented	8	7	9	8	The higher, the lower the risk aversion.	RA	RT	RT
Off-farm activities	31%	35%	25%	28%	The higher, the higher the risk aversion.	RA	RT	RN
Risk aversion %						100%	50%	0%

7 CONCLUSION

This report delves into the intricate interplay of risk aversion analysis, behaviour modelling, and climate change awareness. We focused on the domain of agent-based modelling (ABM), shedding light on the most promising advancements in this field.

At the core of our document lies the description of the ABNexus model, showing its fundamental components. We focused on three crucial modules within the ABNexus model, each embodying distinct behavioural strategies.

The first module aligns with the classical profit-maximizing paradigm, reflecting established economic principles. The second module introduces the element of experience, employing a variety of metrics to evaluate optimal decisions while accounting for farmers' risk preferences. Inspired by Huber et al.(2022) FARMIND model, the third module incorporates a diverse array of heuristic strategies, integrating economic and behavioural theories to offer a sophisticated and nuanced approach to decision-making in the agricultural realm. Its incorporation of prospect theory, social interactions, and individual preferences provides a more realistic and comprehensive representation of farmers' behaviour.

Last, we showed a practical application by extracting distinct risk aversion profiles derived from a survey conducted among farmers in the Adda River domain.

This report contributes to the evolving landscape of ABM, addressing the integration of risk aversion analysis and behaviour modelling. It describes a practical framework with implications for climate change awareness and sustainable decision-making in agriculture.

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